

THE DRILLING OF CARBON FIBRE POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

Alan Chambers¹ and Gordon Bishop²

¹Department of Engineering Materials, University of Southampton, U.K.

²PERA INTERNATIONAL, Melton Mowbray, U.K.

ABSTRACT

The drilling of carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK has been investigated using three different drill types manufactured from cemented carbide and polycrystalline diamond (PCD). The factors considered were drill wear, surface quality and cutting efficiency. It was found that with both composites, the best overall performance was given by the PCD helical flute drill. The wear rate when machining carbon/PEEK were approximately three times greater than that of carbon/epoxy and hence this composite is the more difficult to drill. This is attributed to the role the PEEK matrix plays in the mechanism of abrasive wear.

INTRODUCTION

Although in terms of bulk material removal, machining is less important with composites than with metals, it still causes considerable problems for the composite manufacturing industry. In addition to the problems of tool wear which strongly influences the machining rate and hence the machining cost, it is very difficult to achieve the quality of surface needed for the accurate assembly of panels and structures. It is also important that the machined surface is not damaged as this may contribute to the initiation of a fatigue failure.

The major problems when machining composites are delamination, fibre fracture or tearing, pull out, burr formation and thermal damage. Research has shown that the rate of machining and quality of the surface is a function of the cutting parameters, tool geometry and tool material [1]. Abrasion resistant tool materials such as PCD and cemented carbides are recommended for wear resistance and hence life. Special geometries have been developed to give an effective cutting action which yields a quality surface. The problem is that the effectiveness of a drill geometry is very dependent upon the make-up of the composite and hence each system must be considered separately.

The objective of this research was to investigate the effect of the cutting variables on the drilling of carbon /epoxy and carbon/PEEK. The factors considered were surface quality, drill wear and cutting efficiency.

EXPERIMENTAL

The composites used in this investigation were:

- : carbon/epoxy
- : carbon/PEEK

The laminates, approximately 5mm thick, were manufactured from 0,90 woven prepreg. In both cases the volume fraction of fibres was approximately 60%.

Drilling was performed using a Cincinnati 7VC machining centre to allow accurate reproduction of the feeds and speeds and to facilitate the measurement of the cutting forces. The 6mm diameter drills used in the research were:

- : helical flute drill (118 degree point angle)
- : multi faceted point, straight flute drill (SAAB)
- : dagger drill (30 degree point angle)

Thrust and torque were measured using Kistler instruments piezo-electric quartz dynamometer model 9257A. Drill wear was measured microscopically and the quality of the drilled surface assessed qualitatively using a scanning electron microscope and quantitatively using a surface profilometer..

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THE EFFECT OF DRILL GEOMETRY AND CUTTING PARAMETERS

The effect of drill type upon the cutting forces of carbon/epoxy as a function of time (holes drilled) when drilling with a speed of 50m/min and a feed of .05mm/rev is shown in Fig 1. The dagger drill drilled with a thrust approximately 30% that of the other drill geometries in cemented carbide. The sharp pointed dagger drill breaks through the laminate before the hole has been opened up to its full diameter and hence the resolved vertical component of the cutting force of the dagger will be lower than that of the other geometries which develop the full diameter before breakthrough.

Fig.1 Effect of time on carbon/epoxy thrust

For all the drills it is important to note that the forces increase with cutting time. This is attributed to the effect of wear which reduces the cutting efficiency of the drill [2]. This is considered in more detail in the following sections.

Similar trends were found with carbon/PEEK; the dagger drill again producing the lowest thrust. Typical results produced with a cutting speed of 100m/min and a feed of .094 mm/rev are shown in Fig.2. The initial thrusts (drill unworn) with carbon/PEEK are approximately 40% lower than with carbon/epoxy with all drill geometries. However the rate of increase in thrust as a function of time is much greater for carbon/PEEK. This is indicative of a higher rate of wear with this composite.

Fig.2 Cutting forces for carbon/PEEK

The effect of increasing the feed rate is to increase the thrust and torques with all combinations of drill and composite. These results are in agreement with those of other workers [3]. Although a high thrust might be expected to increase the danger of delamination and damage on entry and exit, it is possible that it will reduce thermal damage because the drill contact time /hole, and hence friction, will also be reduced.

Fig.3 Effect of feed on torque and thrust of carbon/epoxy

It is interesting to note that although the thrust with carbon/PEEK is lower than with carbon/epoxy, the torques are higher. This can probably be explained by the differences in the cutting mechanism; that of carbon/PEEK involving ductile fracture and that of carbon/epoxy being brittle fracture.

DRILL GEOMETRY AND WEAR

The effect of drill geometry on wear when drilling carbon/epoxy at 50 m/min and a feed rate of .05 m/rev is shown in Fig 4. The dagger drill was the most efficient geometry of the cemented carbide drills, producing 3x more holes for an equal amount of wear. The dagger drill has a longer cutting edge and hence the wear is distributed over a greater area. Hence the depth of wear at any point along the cutting edge is reduced.

Fig.4 The effect of drill geometry on wear

Fig 4 also enables a comparison of the wear rates of carbon/PEEK and carbon/epoxy to be made. It can be seen that with the helical flute drill the wear rates of carbon/PEEK are significantly higher than with carbon/epoxy. A similar trend was found with the other drill geometries.

The performance of the drills when machining carbon/PEEK at a cutting speed of 100m/min and a feed of .094mm/rev is shown in Fig 5. The ranking order of the drills in terms of wear resistance is the same as with carbon//epoxy. Fig 5 also demonstrates that carbon/PEEK is more abrasive than carbon/epoxy.

Fig.5 Drill wear with carbon/PEEK at cutting speed of 100m/min and feed of 0.094mm/rev

THE ROLE OF THE TOOL MATERIAL

The effect of the tool material was established by comparing the performance of cemented carbide and PCD helical flute drills.

With regard to the cutting forces there is very little difference in the values generated by new drills in the different tool materials. Also, with both materials, there was initially a steep rise in force with holes drilled due to the breakdown of the sharp cutting edge. Once the steady state, secondary wear regime, is reached the benefits of the greater wear resistance of PCD become apparent and the rate of increase of thrust with time reduced (Fig 2).

Consideration of the wear rates revealed that the wear rate of PCD was much lower than that of cemented carbide (Fig 4). On a wear criterion PCD can be expected to give a minimum of a ten-fold improvement in drill life. This can be attributed to its greater resistance to abrasion wear which dominates the wear process with these materials [4].

PCD drill easily out performed the cemented carbide drill. However, it is important to note that the wear rate of PCD with this composite was higher than with carbon/epoxy. This provides further evidence that carbon/PEEK is more abrasive than carbon/epoxy.

SURFACE QUALITY

Considering firstly the differences in the quality of the internal surfaces of the drilled holes in carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK; with carbon/ PEEK the hole walls were shiny irrespective of the drill type or cutting parameters whereas with carbon/epoxy the appearance was cutting parameter dependent. At a cutting speed of 100m/min and feeds greater than 3mm/sec (.04 mm/rev) the surfaces were reasonably smooth but showed evidence of deformation and fracturing of the matrix. (Fig 6). At low feeds , < 3mm/sec, there was little evidence of epoxy on the cut surface and the exposed fibres could be clearly seen (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6 Carbon/epoxy - high feed

Fig. 7 Carbon/epoxy - low feed

The differences in the surfaces of the carbon/epoxy and the carbon/PEEK can be attributed to the matrix. The smeared appearance given by the PEEK is typical of that given by a thermoplastic softening under the heat generated by the drill, whereas the appearance of the epoxy is typical of a brittle matrix. At low temperatures there is evidence of fracture and at high temperatures the resin has burnt off.

Surface finish measurements made on the hole walls confirmed the visual impressions (Fig. 8). At all feed rates the carbon /PEEK produced a smoother surface than carbon/epoxy. It is interesting that with carbon/epoxy the surfaces are rougher at low feeds. This is believed to be due to the small steps which are left between the plies as the resin is burnt off as a result of the temperatures which are generated under low feed rate conditions.

Fig.8 Effect of feed rate on hole roughness at a cutting speed of 100m/min

The relationship between surface finish in the hole and properties such as fatigue life has not been fully established. It has been reported [1] that the surfaces produced under low feeds and high feeds (high thrust) have a more adverse effect than those produced with high speeds and low feeds (low thrust). This would suggest that damage such as delamination as might occur with a high thrust is more serious than thermal damage as might occur with high speeds and low feeds and hence a low thrust.

The burr heights on entry and exit were also measured and the results for carbon/PEEK drilled at 100m/min and .094mm/rev feed are given in Figure 9. It can be seen that the cleanest holes were given by the helical flute drills in cemented carbide and PCD. It should be noted that the SAAB and Dagger drills performed poorly in this respect. With all the drill geometries the burr heights were significantly less with carbon/epoxy.

THE ROLE OF THE MATRIX

The matrix plays a significant role in the machinability of a carbon fibre polymer matrix composite material through its influence on the cutting mechanism. With respect to wear, it is thought that the ductile matrix, PEEK, provides support for the carbon fibres, allowing them to bend in the direction of drill motion and hence present a greater surface area to the drill than is the case with the epoxy. With carbon/epoxy, fracture dominates under drilling conditions which generate low temperatures and hence the fibres are cut cleanly. Under conditions which generate high temperatures resin burn off reduces support for the fibres. High rates of abrasion occur when the abrasive is firmly anchored by the matrix as is the

case with carbon fibres in a PEEK matrix.

Fig. 9 The effect of drill geometry on entry/exit damage of carbon/PEEK

The other main effect of the matrix is in its influence on the quality of the machined surface. It is clear that during drilling that the PEEK softens and flows to produce a smooth surface. This is expected to be good from the point of view of resisting the initiation of fatigue cracks. The disadvantage of PEEK concerns the quality of the holes on entry and exit. Burring on entry and exit is essentially the result of a peeling action. On entry, the drill pushes down and cuts into the laminate, pulling the partially machined material upward along the flute resulting in separation of the upper lamina from that below it. On exit, as the drill approaches exit, the resistance to deformation decreases and there is the possibility that the interlaminar bond strength will be exceeded and delamination will occur. The role of the matrix is to determine whether cutting involves clean fracture or whether it involves deformation and tearing. The latter dominates with PEEK.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRILL GEOMETRY

In many respects the sharp pointed dagger drill outperformed the helical and straight fluted drills because it cut with lower forces and generated less wear. However, the positive attributes of this drill, are more than outweighed by the unacceptable quality of the surfaces produced on entry and exit. The sharp pointed dagger drill displaces the laminate rather than creating the fracture which would result in a cleaner cut.

A comparison of the helical and straight fluted drills showed very little difference in performance with the exception of entry and exit burring. The helical drill was clearly superior in this respect and hence is considered to give the best overall performance.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been found that the drilling of carbon fibre composites is dependent upon the characteristics of the matrix. The thermoplastic matrix provides more support for the fibres during drilling which results in higher rates of abrasive wear. Carbon/PEEK produced smoother surfaces within the hole but produced more damage on entry and exit.

The helical drill geometry gave the best overall performance taking into account both wear and surface quality. The wear rates of the PCD drills were significantly lower than those of the cemented carbide drills and is the preferred tool material.

REFERENCES

1. A. R. Chambers, Factors influencing the surface quality of drilled holes in carbon fibre reinforced polymers. *Proc. ECCM 6, Bordeaux, 185-190*, (1993).
2. S. J. Jamil, Evaluation of surfaces quality of drilled holes in composite materials after high speed drilling. *Proc 2nd International Conf. on the Behaviour of Materials in Machining, York, 70-76*, (1991).
3. T. Radhakrishnan and S. M. Wu, *ASME Journal of Engineering for Industry*, **103**, 119-125, (1981).
4. K. Sukarmo, M. Seto, Y. Tangiguchi and Y. Yookoo, *Trans Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers*, **51**, 656-666, (1985).